

Dasara

By Caleb Simmons, University of Arizona

Entry tags: Bhakti traditions, Hindu Tantric traditions, Hindu Śākta traditions, Modern Hinduism, Religious Group, Śaiva traditions, Liṅgāyat or Vīraśaiva, Hinduism, Indic Religious Traditions

Dasara is celebrated by many people in southern Karnataka, especially in the city of Mysore. The celebrants include people from all castes and religious communities, including brahmin priests, royalty, agricultural castes, people of the city, etc.

Date Range: 1610 CE - 2016 CE

Region: Mysore

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India

The Mysore Kingdom according to the 1799 Treaty of Seringpatam.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: C. Hayavadana Rao. *The Dasara in Mysore: Its Origin and Significance* (Bangalore: Bangalore Printing & Publishing, 1936).
- Source 2: Caleb Simmons. "The Goddess on the Hill: The (Re)invention of a local goddess as Cāmuṅḍī." in *Inventing and Reinventing the Local Goddess ed Sree Padma* (New York: Lexington Books, 2014).
- Source 3: Aya Ikegame. *Princely India Re-imagined: A Historical Anthropology of Mysore from 1799 to the Present* (New York: Routledge, 2013).

Reference: Simmons, Caleb. "Domains of Dasara: Reflections on the Struggle for Significance in Contemporary Mysore". In *Nine Nights of Power*. Albany, NY: SUNY Press, 2021.

Reference: "The King and the Yadu Line: Performing Lineage Through Dasara in Nineteenth-century Mysore". In *Nine Nights of the Goddess: Navarātri Festival in South Asia*, 63–82. Albany, NY: SUNY Press, 2018.

Reference: Simmons, Caleb. *Devotional Sovereignty: Kingship and Religion in India*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2019.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.mysoredasara.gov.in>
- Source 1 Description: Official Mysore Dasara Webpage
- Source 2 URL: <http://keonline.in>

– Source 2 Description: Karnataka State Exhibition Authority Dasara Webpage

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://203.200.22.249:8080/jspui/handle/2014/6154>

– Source 1 Description: The Annals of the Mysore Royal Family: The Kannada history of the Mysore Wodeyars from the beginning of time to the reign of Kṛṣṇarāja III.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The primary sources for ritual apparatus for Mysore's Dasara is the Kālikāpurāṇa and Śaivāgamas.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: There are also many oral tales about the celebration of Dasara, including ritual oral traditions

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: In the Purāṇic tradition, the texts are narrated and/or conversations amongst deities; therefore, they are often viewed as having their origin from divine beings.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There is Cāmuṇḍēśvari's temple and the Mysore Palace

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 12000

Notes: This is the approximate size of the entire Mysore Palace, which is the central religious monument of the Dasara celebration

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 53.5

Notes: Height of the spires of the Mysore Palace, which is the central religious monument of the Dasara celebration

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

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Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Dasara is a time when many social and political hierarchies are enacted. This includes interactions between different sects within Hinduism and different religions.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: While there is competition, many different traditions (including different caste traditions) take part in the celebration.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: While there is not much (if any) violent conflict in modern India, Dasara marked the beginning of the military season in medieval and late medieval Mysore.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

–Yes [specify]: Palace

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1500000

Notes: Approximately 1 million to 1.5 million people visit the official contemporary Dasara celebration in Mysore every year. However, participation in the festival is nearly ubiquitous for all people of the region in some capacity.

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000000

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Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: There are, of course, ways that this is already assigned. The ways that Dasara is celebrated reaffirms these affiliations.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: In modern Karnataka and Mysore, however, the "state festival" is officially advertised and many crore rupees are spent in tourism advertising.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Participation in the festival is nearly ubiquitous for all people of the region in some capacity.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: During this festival the king would "honor gift" important people, including priests, in his kingdom

Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Part of the infrastructure is provided by the state

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: This is debatable to a certain extent, but there remains a clear distinction between the officiants and the royalty (pre-Independence) and politicians (contemporary)

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: Certainly during the medieval and late medieval periods Dasara was time when polity provided special economic treatment during Dasara, including tax revenues from land grants.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
– Yes
Notes: Cāmuṇḍēśvari in the form of the buffalo-slayer

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
– No

↳ Humans:
– Yes
Notes: The Mahārāja of Mysore

↳ Other features of iconography:
– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:
– No

Nature of religious group [please select one]:
– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:
– Yes

Notes: Dasara is all about establishing hierarchies. Amongst the important leaders are the king (Mahārāja), the head priest of the Cāmuṇḍēśvari temple, and the head of the Parakala maṭha.

Membership/Group Interactions

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Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

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– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: The Mahārāja of Mysore

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Since Dasara is a large festival celebrated by many different sects and subjects, there are many different interpretations of the events, myths, and practices.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Since Dasara is celebrated by so many different people, there is a wide variety of beliefs about the spirit-mind division

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– No

Notes: Prosocial norms are regulated by karma theory

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: There are many tales about the deities protecting their devotees and punishing those that would do them harm.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: In many medieval cases, the rituals of Dasara were conducted to gain a boon of victory

over rival polities.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Notes: The deities (especially the goddess), however, are concerned and help their devotees conceive children.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Dasara is a time when many people make oaths to the goddess. The goddess expects them to keep their oaths.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: The opening ritual of the tenth day (actually Dasara) is a boxing match between two wrestlers. The official Dasara day celebration begins when blood from the wrestlers hits the earth.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Not in general, but ritual purity is extremely important.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The deities are all viewed within the region as related to one another by birth or by marriage.

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: For many Dasara participants, there is a high god, who is envisioned as the Goddess, Viṣṇu, or Śiva.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
 - Notes: But they are homologous

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Wodeyar kings are said to come from the Lunar line and descend from Mahāviṣṇu and Kṛṣṇa

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - No

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

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- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a pantheon of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: There are, of course, plenty of social norms in this society more broadly. Dasara does exist within this constructs.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Since Dasara is a large festival celebrated by many different sects and subjects, there are many different interpretations of the events, myths, and practices.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The goddess punishes the rivals and enemies of her devotees. This is secured through proper devotion and ritual practice during Dasara

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

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Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

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- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
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- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes
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- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Most will have this, but it is not part of the festival

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Viraśaivas

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Not as part of the festival.

Are formal burials present:

– No

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Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

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– No

Notes: But they are homologous

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Notes: The Wodeyar kings are said to come from the Lunar line and descend from Mahāviṣṇu and Kṛṣṇa

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a pantheon of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– No

Notes: Prosocial norms are regulated by karma theory

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: There are many tales about the deities protecting their devotees and punishing those that would do them harm.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: In many medieval cases, the rituals of Dasara were conducted to gain a boon of victory over rival polities.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Notes: The deities (especially the goddess), however, are concerned and help their devotees conceive children.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Dasara is a time when many people make oaths to the goddess. The goddess expects them to keep their oaths.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: The opening ritual of the tenth day (actually Dasara) is a boxing match between two wrestlers. The official Dasara day celebration begins when blood from the wrestlers hits the earth.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Not in general, but ritual purity is extremely important.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The deities are all viewed within the region as related to one another by birth or by marriage.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The goddess punishes the rivals and enemies of her devotees. This is secured through proper devotion and ritual practice during Dasara

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: There are, of course, plenty of social norms in this society more broadly. Dasara does exist within this constructs.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: During Dasara daily rituals are observed, but due to the wide range of people and practices there is great variance in the amount of time spent per day during the 10 day festival.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: During Dasara daily rituals are observed, but due to the wide range of people and practices there is great variance in the size of these large-scale rituals from a few hundred people at the rituals atop Cāmuṇḍi Hills to the 200,000 people who observe the Dasara procession.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: During Dasara daily rituals are observed, but due to the wide range of people and practices there is great variance in the amount of time spent per day during the 10 day festival.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: For some celebrants the use of alcohol is necessary, especially on the 7th night called Kālarātri.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

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– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

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– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: During Dasara daily rituals are observed, but due to the wide range of people and practices there is great variance in the amount of time spent per day during the 10 day festival.

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I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

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Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

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– No

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– Yes

Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: For some celebrants the use of alcohol is necessary, especially on the 7th night called Kālarātri.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The celebration of Dasara in Mysore has always been connected with the state, whether it was the Mysore Kingdom or the state of Karnataka

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Parts of Dasara include educational and cultural exhibitions

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: There source material is found in Sanskrit and Kannada

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Dasara and its attendant rituals follow a very strict ritual calendar.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Do the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The state of Karnataka officially organizes and runs the Dasara celebration

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: During Dasara, exhibitions are set up to teach a variety of things from clean water usage to seed storing to cooking exhibitions.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The city of Mysore provides public transportation to all the Dasara events.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The celebration of Dasara in Mysore has always been connected with the state, whether it was the Mysore Kingdom or the state of Karnataka

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Parts of Dasara include educational and cultural exhibitions

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: During Dasara, exhibitions are set up to teach a variety of things from clean water usage to seed storing to cooking exhibitions.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The state of Karnataka officially organizes and runs the Dasara celebration

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The city of Mysore provides public transportation to all the Dasara events.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: There source material is found in Sanskrit and Kannada

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Dasara and its attendant rituals follow a very strict ritual calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Source 1: C. Hayavadana Rao. *The Dasara in Mysore: Its Origin and Significance* (Bangalore: Bangalore Printing & Publishing, 1936)., Source 2: Caleb Simmons. "The Goddess on the Hill: The (Re)invention of a local goddess as Cāmuṇḍī." in *Inventing and Reinventing the Local Goddess* ed Sree Padma (New York: Lexington Books, 2014)., Source 3: Aya Ikegame. *Princely India Re-imagined: A Historical Anthropology of Mysore from 1799 to the Present* (New York: Routledge, 2013)., Simmons, Caleb. "Domains of Dasara: Reflections on the Struggle for Significance in Contemporary Mysore". In *Nine Nights of Power*. Albany, NY: SUNY Press, 2021.

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